

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA FOR SEASONAL ALLERGIC RHINITIS

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Abstract Allergic rhinitis (AR) is a fairly common pathology of the body in which the target organ is the nasal cavity, characterized by a symptom complex involving swelling of the mucous membrane and nasal congestion, itching in the nasal cavity and sneezing, rhinorrhea and difficulty in nasal breathing.

Keywords. Allergic rhinitis, seasonal diseases, diagnostic criteria.

According to N.D. Suyunova and co-authors (2017), the prevalence of AR in the Republic of Uzbekistan was: “in the city of Tashkent - 0.95%, in the Bukhara region - 2.36%, in the Jizzakh region - 1.12%, in the Navoi region - 3.12% , in the Surkhandarya region - 1.4%, in the Khorezm region - 2.32%, severe hay fever was diagnosed in 29.5%, the number of average bed days - 6 days, rural population - 43%, urban population - 57%, associated diseases: conjunctivitis – 50%, atopic dermatitis – 10%, bronchial asthma (BA) – 30%” [17].

In 2009-2014 in our country, an increase in the incidence of AR was recorded at 13.5% (from 98.5 to 111.83 per 100,000 inhabitants) [8]. In Uzbekistan, studies were conducted on the incidence of AR in preschool children with pathologies of the ENT organs and a high incidence of SAR and PAR was noted even at this age [6, 7]. In the city of Tashkent, 42.7% of primary school students suffer from AR, more often boys, as well as 57.3% of 13-14 year old schoolchildren with a predominance of girls [10, 20].

By us for the period 2020–2023. 126 patients with SAR aged 21–50 years were examined (average age 31.6 ± 1.4 years), of which there were 52 men, 74 women. The average age of the observed men was 33.7 ± 1.3 years, women – 29.2 ± 1.5 years (Table 1).

The control group consisted of 32 practically healthy individuals, whose average age was determined to be 31.3 ± 1.6 years, without impaired nasal breathing and changes in the nasal cavity and nasopharynx during rhinoscopy.

When studying the anamnesis of SAR patients, we found that the median age of clinical manifestation of SAR was 20 (14-28) years. The age limit for the manifestation of any manifestations of allergies (often urticaria) in the studied patients was 1-12 years (56.1%; 95% CI = 50.9-61.7), i.e. childhood and adolescence. The onset of SAD was recorded at 11-16 years of age (40.6%; 95%CI=35.4-45.9).

Heredity was aggravated in 51.59% (95% CI = 48.43-59.71) of patients with SAR in ascending relatives, of the remaining 48.41%, in 14.3% we found allergic pathologies in cousins (95 %CI:12.63-16.12; $\chi^2=12.14$; $p=0.05$).

Our mathematical statistical analysis led us to the conclusion that the hereditary history of the patient's closest relatives sixfold increases his risk of developing SAD (OR = 5.985; 95% CI: 5.64-8.91). In the presence of a diagnosed allergic pathology in the mother, in the absence of allergic pathology in the father, the risk practically does not reduce - it becomes fivefold (OR = 5.219; 95% CI: 4.68-12.14).

The presence of allergic pathologies in other relatives also increases the risk in patients, but the degree of influence in this case is somewhat lesser.

In the course of our study, we identified a certain family chain of risk for the formation of SAD and allergic pathologies - both parents - OR = 5.985, mother only - OR = 5.219, father only - OR = 4.214, sibling - OR = 3.642, sibling - OR = 2.456, maternal aunt and/or uncle - OR=1.897, paternal aunt and/or uncle - OR=1.127.

The patients with SAD studied presented with a wide variety of complaints, which together sharply worsened their quality of life (QoL). The most common symptom, as expected, was rhinorrhea - 91.27% (95% CI = 89.29-95.22), with 93.75% of urban residents and 90.43% in rural areas, the next most prominent symptoms were congestion nose and difficulty in nasal breathing - 87.30% (95% CI = 85.58-92.19), 90.63% of urban residents and 86.17% of rural residents, itchy eyes - 83.33% (95% CI =80.89-88.68), lacrimation - 73.81% (95%CI=71.29-80.48).

We also noted pollen intoxication in 54.76% (95%CI=52.78-63.29) of the subjects, and swelling of the eyelids in 51.69% (95%CI=49.78-60.39). Exactly half of the subjects (95% CI = 47.88-58.79) presented the classic complaint of itching in the nose, with 53.13% of urban and 48.94% of rural residents.

The rarest complaints were contact dermatitis - in 1.59% (95% CI = 0.83-3.95), somewhat more often - in 4.76% (95% CI = 4.12-8.23) patients complained for urticaria, which can be explained by the age of the subjects and the purpose of selecting patients with SAD.

Also, in 37.3% (47 people) (95% CI = 32.48-42.88) of the studied patients with SAD, we found allergic reactions to food products, and in the majority to 2 or more food products of plant origin.

Thus, according to the severity of the exacerbation of SAR, the studied patients were divided into mild course (LS) - 23 (18.25%), moderate severity (ST) of SAR - 73 (57.94%) patients and severe course (ST) of SAR - 30 (23.81%).

In patients with RT SAR, the average duration of exacerbation was 24.78 ± 3.42 days, in ST SAR - 31.89 ± 3.87 days, and in TT SAR - 46.88 ± 4.12 days. At the same time, the number of exacerbations of SAR in patients with RT averaged 1.23 ± 0.48 times per year, in the group with ST course of SAR - 1.65 ± 0.72 times per year, in patients with TT SAR - 2.34 ± 0.95 times a year.

Conclusion . Based on the parametric and non-parametric correlation analysis, we came to the conclusion that based on the presence of a significant correlation between the number of eosinophils in impression smears from the nasal cavity (i.e. in the secretion of the nasal cavity) with all functional, instrumental, clinical and laboratory indicators for rapid and accurate diagnosis of the severity of exacerbation of SAR and the magnitude of persistent inflammation in the nasal mucosa during remission. In the vast majority of cases, it is sufficient to perform a microscopy of a smear-imprint from the nasal cavity, stained only according to Romanovsky- Giemsa , to determine the number of eosinophils in the field of view for laboratory confirmation of AR, as a non-invasive , most sensitive and accurate analysis, and available at any level of healthcare in the Republic of Uzbekistan .

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